

THE ROLE OF RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS IN FORECASTING BUSINESS STABILITY

Moroz K.

Master's degree,

National Technical University Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute

Abstract

The article explores the role of retrospective analysis (RA) of financial statements (FS) in forecasting business stability (BSF), using American corporations as an example. It examines methods of analyzing historical data to identify factors influencing financial stability. Tools such as sensitivity analysis, scenario analysis, and statistical modeling are analyzed, along with their application for improving forecast accuracy. Examples from American corporations illustrate how RA helps adapt to market changes, enhancing risk management and financial performance. The advantages and limitations of this method are discussed.

Keywords: retrospective analysis (RA), business stability forecasting (BSF), financial statements (FS), scenario analysis, statistical modeling, risk management.

Introduction

Retrospective analysis (RA) of financial statements (FS) plays a crucial role in the strategic management of modern corporations, especially in the face of economic instability and heightened competition in global markets. This approach involves studying historical data about a company in order to identify trends, patterns and important factors affecting business stability. The complexity of business operations, intensified by market fluctuations, legislative changes, and macroeconomic shocks, necessitates a more balanced approach to forecasting and planning for companies.

The relevance of studying RA in the context of FS stems from the need to enhance forecast accuracy, especially during times of crisis. Today, companies strive not only to understand their current business situation but also to predict its long-term stability. This is especially pertinent for large corporations whose decisions significantly impact the global economy. The objective of this research article is to analyze the role of RA in the context of FS in forecasting business stability (BSF), using American corporations as an example.

Main part. The role of FS in assessing BSF

The main source of information for assessing the current state and stability of the company is its FS. It reflects the financial condition of the company using indicators such as liquidity, solvency and profitability, which allow you to assess the company's ability to meet its short- and long-term obligations, as well as its ability to generate profit. **Liquidity** reflects a company's ability to cover its short-term liabilities with its current assets and is one of the most significant indicators for assessing short-term business stability. **Solvency** reflects the company's ability to meet its debt obligations in the long term and is a crucial indicator for evaluating the financial stability of a business, particularly in conditions of high debt load or when attracting new loans.

Profitability characterizes the company's ability to generate profit and use its resources efficiently.

Changes in financial indicators directly influence the forecasts of a company's stability. For instance, a decline in liquidity may signal a short-term default risk, while deteriorating profitability metrics may indicate a decline in the company's market competitiveness. If a company shows negative trends across several indicators, this may warrant adjustments in risk management strategies and the development of new asset management approaches. Such changes may predict the need for business restructuring, including asset optimization, cost reduction, and changes in the company's investment policy [1]. Thus, the use of FS allows analysts and managers to identify weaknesses in the business promptly, take corrective actions, and develop strategies aimed at improving efficiency and long-term stability. This makes FS not only a tool for analyzing the current state but also a foundation for developing plans aimed at the company's successful long-term growth.

Theoretical foundations of RA

The method of studying past financial data of a company to identify trends, patterns, and indicators affecting its performance is known as RA. Its primary goal is to evaluate the company's past financial results and, based on this, assess opportunities for improving future performance. This analysis helps to better understand how management decisions and external factors have influenced the company's financial state in the past, laying the groundwork for more accurate future forecasts. Therefore, RA serves as an important tool for strategic planning and risk management. It includes several methods that allow for evaluating the business condition from various perspectives (table 1).

Table 1.

Methods RA [2, 3]		
Method	Description	Example of indicators
Horizontal analysis	Comparison of financial indicators over several periods to identify dynamics and trends.	Revenue, net profit, cost.
Vertical analysis	Estimation of the shares of individual reporting items in relation to general indicators in one period.	Share of cost in revenue, share of assets.
Coefficient analysis	Using financial ratios to assess liquidity, profitability and sustainability.	Liquidity, profitability, and asset turnover ratios.

According to the author, each method of analysis allows for different interpretations of historical data, providing a multifaceted understanding of business dynamics and internal structure. The combined use of these methods helps a company not only to uncover hidden trends and inefficiencies but also to more accurately BSF and readiness for external economic challenges.

The impact of RA of financial statements on BSF

Analyzing historical data is a crucial tool for improving the accuracy of financial forecasts, as it allows for the use of past data to better understand patterns and identify potential errors in forecasting. By analyzing past results, companies can evaluate which factors most significantly impact financial indicators and adjust their forecasting models accordingly (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The role of RA of statements in BSF [4]

This method helps identify inaccuracies in previous forecasts by analyzing discrepancies between expected and actual figures. Such an approach allows for adjustments and refinements to forecasting models, adapting them to new conditions. It enhances the effectiveness of decision-making processes. By using historical data, companies can make more informed and well-reasoned decisions, minimizing risks and improving the precision of resource management. Studying past data also aids in identifying long-term trends, allowing for better forecasting of future changes. Adjustments based on RA help companies quickly adapt to market changes, which, in turn, enhances business resilience and competitiveness.

To forecast BSF based on RA, various tools are used to account for multiple factors and possible outcomes. One such tool is **scenario analysis**, which allows a company to model various business development scenarios based on past data. This method involves creating multiple scenarios that assess the impact of external and internal factors on the company's financial condition. Scenario analysis helps prepare for potential risks and develop strategies for different situations. An example of using scenario analysis is **General Electric**, which has applied this method to assess the impact of macroeconomic changes and commodity price fluctuations on its production units. This approach helped the company adapt to economic changes and

minimize risks associated with energy price fluctuations [5].

Another tool is **statistical modeling**. It involves using retrospective data to create predictive models. Methods such as regression analysis, time series, and econometric models allow companies to forecast future financial performance based on historical data. This method helps identify causal relationships between various financial indicators and build detailed forecasts. For instance, **Microsoft** uses statistical modeling to predict demand for its cloud services. By utilizing retrospective data on service consumption, the company develops models that predict future demand and adjust its operational processes to maintain sustainable growth [6].

Sensitivity analysis, a forecasting method that involves changing one or more parameters in financial models to assess how various changes will impact business stability, is another approach. For example, changes in raw material prices, interest rates, or demand can significantly alter forecasts.

Thus, RA is a powerful tool for BSF as it relies on real data and proven methods, such as scenario analysis and statistical modeling. This approach allows companies to respond flexibly to changes in the external environment, manage risks, and develop more substantiated strategic plans. Such analysis of FS is widely used in American corporations for BSF forecasting and growth strategy development. It enables companies to evaluate

the effectiveness of past decisions, identify trends, and develop plans to minimize risks and improve efficiency.

A successful example of such companies is **Apple**, which actively uses RA to forecast demand for its products and adapt its business strategy. The company analyzes past sales of iPhones, iPads, and Macs to understand seasonal demand fluctuations and the impact of economic factors. It has used retrospective data to plan the release of new models in line with changing market and consumer needs. This approach allowed Apple to adapt to the saturation of the smartphone market and focus on developing services like Apple Music and iCloud, contributing to revenue diversification [7].

Another example is **Walmart**, which effectively utilizes RA of financial statements to enhance the stability and resilience of its business operations. By conducting a thorough analysis of historical financial data, including past sales figures, revenue trends, and expense patterns, Walmart has been able to refine its forecasting models, particularly in inventory management and logistics. This approach allows the company to identify and anticipate demand fluctuations across different regions and seasons, which are critical for maintaining business stability. By understanding these financial trends, Walmart can make more informed decisions about stock levels, ensuring that resources are not tied up in excess inventory while also avoiding shortages that could disrupt operations. The insights gained from RA enable Walmart to adjust its logistics strategies, optimizing transportation routes and schedules to minimize costs and maximize efficiency [8].

American companies illustrate that RA of financial data has become a vital instrument for effective management and BSF. This approach to financial statement analysis offers several benefits, including high precision and objectivity. It enables the identification of long-term patterns and trends, supports risk management by anticipating potential threats, and facilitates the development of mitigation strategies. Furthermore, RA is adaptable to diverse scenarios and produces results that are straightforward to interpret, ensuring clarity and accessibility for stakeholders.

However, despite its strengths, RA also presents limitations. Its dependence on historical data may not adequately capture future market dynamics, particularly during periods of rapid economic change, technological disruptions, financial crises, or regulatory transformations. This retrospective focus may result in over-reliance on past performance, potentially creating a misleading sense of stability if emerging threats or opportunities are not adequately considered. Moreover, RA often does not integrate qualitative factors such as shifts in consumer behavior, geopolitical influences, or strategic industry changes – elements that are critical for anticipating future business conditions. Therefore, while RA serves as a valuable foundation for analysis, it must be supplemented with proactive methodologies,

such as scenario analysis and real-time data analytics, to offer a more robust and comprehensive perspective on business resilience and adaptability.

Conclusion

The use of RA is an important assessment and BSF tool, as evidenced by the experience of leading American corporations. The use of historical data allows companies to identify important trends, evaluate the effectiveness of previous decisions and develop strategies to manage risks and increase stability. Examples of companies such as Apple, Microsoft, and General Electric show that RA facilitates timely adaptation to market changes and helps strengthen competitive positions.

Despite the evident advantages of RA, such as accuracy, objectivity, and the ability to manage risks, its application requires consideration of limitations related to dependence on past data and the inability to predict abrupt economic changes. Nevertheless, when combined with other forecasting methods, RA remains a powerful means for strengthening financial stability and enhancing business competitiveness.

References

1. Venter E. R., Van Eck L. Research on extended external reporting assurance: Trends, themes, and opportunities // *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*. 2021. T. 32. №. 1. P. 63-103.
2. Dudaiti G. Launching services in complex regions: Strategies and challenges for ride-hailing businesses in USA // *Sciences of Europe*. 2024. № 146. P. 19-22.
3. Odonkor B., Kaggwa S., Uwaoma P. U., Hassan A. O., Farayola O. A review of advanced accounting techniques in US economic resilience // *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*. 2024. T. 6. №. 1. P. 40-55.
4. Pshychenko D. V. The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Crisis Management in the Economy // *Trends in the Development of Science and Education*. 2024. №. 112(3). P. 117-122.
5. Salimi M., Moradi M. A., Amidpour M. Modeling and outlook analysis of gasoline supply and demand and sensitivity analysis of main economic and social drivers // *Energy*. 2022. T. 256. P. 124686.
6. Nawrocki P., Smendowski M. Optimization of the use of cloud computing resources using exploratory data analysis and machine learning // *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing Research*. 2024. T. 14. №. 4. P. 287-308.
7. He F. iPhone Sales Prediction Based on Multilinear Regression Model: Evidence from Statista // *2023 IEEE International Conference on Sensors, Electronics and Computer Engineering (ICSECE)*. IEEE, 2023. P. 341-346.
8. Frimpong V. Artificial Intelligence in Business History Analysis: Implications for Contemporary Management and Ethical Leadership. 2024.